

FLEXURAL IMPACT PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE BEHAVIORS OF CONTINUOUS AND DISCONTINUOUS RANDOM REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC CFRP

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTP), which combine high performance and high productivity, are expected to be applied to transport vehicles, and it becomes more and more important to understand impact characteristics and temperature characteristics to guarantee their performance. In this study, 3-point bending impact test was performed at various strain-rate and temperature conditions in order to evaluate strain-rate and temperature dependence of three kinds of CFRTP made from the same matrix resin and the same carbon fiber but different type of reinforcement configuration. In addition, fracture observation by using a high speed video camera and fractography were also conducted. As a result of 3-point bending impact test, it was confirmed that the flexural strength and flexural modulus in every CFRTP tend to show lower values at lower strain-rate and higher temperature and higher values at higher strain-rate and lower temperature. It was also confirmed that the starting point of fracture or the state of fracture surface changed depending on test condition. However, the tendencies of flexural properties as functions of strain-rate and temperature were different for each material, and the effect of the reinforcement configuration on strain-rate and temperature dependence was clarified.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites are known as a superior material in specific strength and specific stiffness and applied for vehicle weight reduction. However, most of them are thermosetting CFRP composites with low productivity and high cost, and their applications are limited to aircraft or some transportation vehicles. Therefore, thermoplastic CFRP (CFRTP) composites with high productivity and high performance have been developed and expected to be applied to mass-produced vehicles [1]. However, in order to proceed with application in automobiles, it is necessary to clarify the performance in various temperature environments such as desert and cold climate and the safety in a collision accident. For that purpose, it is important to perform impact test under various temperature environments and accurately grasp the characteristics of the material. The authors examined the strain rate and temperature dependence of CFRTP in flexural strength and failure mode by performing 3-point bending impact test under the temperature environment [2- 4]. In this study, we report the results of 3-point bending impact test of three kinds of CFRTP made from the same matrix resin and the same carbon fiber but different type of reinforcement configuration. In addition, the

fracture behaviors of the materials are clarified from high-speed imaging and fractography, and the influences on the impact properties of their different reinforcement configurations are investigated.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

Three kinds of CFRTP (All materials are manufactured by Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation.) were used for the experiment. Figure 1 shows a model of each material. In all materials, the same matrix resin (Polypropylene) is reinforced with the same carbon fiber (TR 50). Their features are (a) unidirectional laminated material (UD), (b) quasi-isotropic laminated material (QISO), (c) long fiber randomly oriented material (OCT, Fiber length: 25 mm). The specimen information is summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1: Model of each material.
(a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

Specimen Type	Size [mm]	CF	Matrix	V_f [%]
UD	$15 \times 100 \times 1.8$	TR50	Polypropylene	45
QISO	$30 \times 80 \times 1.5$	TR50	Polypropylene	48
OCT	$50 \times 90 \times 2.0$	TR50	Polypropylene	35

Table 1: Specimen information.

2.2 Testing systems

In order to investigate strain rate and temperature dependence, a testing machine is required to set a wide range of test speed and temperature control. A static testing machine AG-Xplus (Shimadzu Corporation) was used for the low test speed experiment, and a high-speed puncture impact testing machine HITS-P 10 (Shimadzu Corporation) was used for the high test speed experiment. The HITS-P 10 is a hydraulically controlled impact testing machine which has characteristics of little velocity reduction during the indenter's stroke. Each testing machine is equipped with a thermostatic chamber that can control temperature. Figure 2 shows the state of testing machines. In front of the impact testing machine, a high-speed video camera (FASTCAM SA-X, Photron) and two metal halide illuminations were installed, and the fracture behavior was observed. Referring to 3-point bending impact test method (JIS K 7084) of carbon fiber reinforced plastics, the 3-point bending test fixture had a radius of 5mm for the indenter and a radius of 2mm for the support [5]. The span was set at 40 mm to enable testing up to high strain rate. Figure 3 shows the fixture for 3-point bending impact test. This fixture is equipped with a mechanism to hold the specimen with a spring so that the specimen does not move by the initial impact.

Figure 2: State of testing machines.
 (a) Static testing machine AG-Xplus (b) High speed impact testing machine HITS-P10

Figure 3: Flexural fixture for 3-point bending impact test.

2.3 Test condition

Test conditions are shown in Table 2. The temperature condition was 6 levels of -30, 0, 25, 50 and 75, 100 °C, and the strain rate was set at 10/s at the maximum.

Specimen Type	UD, QISO, OCT
Test Speed (Strain Rate [s])	0.0001 (QISO, OCT) 0.001 (OCT) 0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10
Temperature [°C]	-30, 0, RT, 50, 75, 100
Span [mm]	40
Number of test	n = 1 (UD) n = 3 (QISO, OCT)

Table 2: Test condition.

3 RESULTS AND CONSIDERATION

3.1 Test results of 3-point bending impact test

As an example of the results of 3-point bending impact tests, stress-strain curves of all temperature at a strain rate of 1/s are shown in Figure 4. From Figure 4, it is confirmed that the flexural strength of

all specimens increases at lower temperature and decreases at higher temperature. And, on UD and OCT, the flexural modulus is higher at lower temperature, and lower at higher temperature. However, in this temperature range, there is no difference in the inclination on QISO, and it is assumed that the change of the elastic modulus by the temperature is small. Similarly, stress-strain curves of all strain rates at room temperature are shown in Figure 5. It is assumed from Figure 5 that the flexural strength is lower at lower strain rate and higher at higher strain rate. On OCT, the flexural modulus is lower at lower strain rate and higher at higher strain rate. However, on the flexural modulus of UD and QISO, it was confirmed that there was little difference in the inclination in this strain rate range and the change of the flexural modulus by the strain rate was small.

Figure 6 shows the flexural strength at each temperature. It is confirmed that the flexural strength of all specimens tends to increase at lower temperature and higher strain rate. And, it was confirmed that the flexural strength was easy to change depending on the temperature condition than the strain rate condition. Similarly, Figure 7 shows the flexural modulus at each temperature. On UD and OCT, it was confirmed that the flexural modulus was higher at lower temperatures and lower at higher temperatures under all strain rate conditions. The flexural modulus of OCT increased at higher strain rate, while the flexural modulus of UD remained almost unchanged in this strain rate range. On the other hand, QISO showed little change in flexural modulus regardless of strain rate and temperature conditions.

Figure 4: Flexural stress-flexural strain curves at strain rate 1 /s.
(a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

Figure 5: Flexural stress-flexural strain curves at room temperature.
(a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

Figure 6: Relationship between flexural strength and strain rate.
(a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

Figure 7: Relationship between flexural modulus and strain rate.
 (a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

3.2 High speed imaging of fracture behavior

In case of room temperature, the fracture behavior of the specimen was observed using the high-speed video camera. As an example of fracture observation, Figure 8 shows images of the moment of fracture when the strain rate is high. It is confirmed from Figure 8 that UD and QISO have an origin of fracture on the compression side (indenter side). However, it is proven that the failure spreads wide in-plane in QISO, while in UD the fracture progresses just under the indenter. On the other hand, fracture of OCT occurred from the tensile side. Similarly, Figure 9 shows images of the moment of fracture when the strain rate is low. At low speed, it was confirmed that the origin of fracture in all specimens was on the compression side. Table 3 shows a summary about the origin of fracture for each specimen at room temperature. UD and QISO specimens were fractured at the compression side from low to high strain rate, while OCT specimen was fractured not only at the compression side but also at the tensile side or by delamination at strain rates of more than 1 /s. In addition, the fracture behavior of UD was observed under 2 conditions of strain rate 1 /s (-8.2 °C) and strain rate 0.01/s (75 °C). Figure 10 shows images of the moment of fracture. From Figure 10, it was confirmed that UD was broken from an onset at compression side at all conditions.

Figure 8: Fracture image at high strain rate.
 (a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

Figure 9: Fracture image at low strain rate.
(a) UD (b) QISO (c) OCT

Specimen Type	strain rate [1/s]						
	0.01	0.05	0.1	0.5	1	5	10
UD	–	Compression	–	Compression	–	Compression	–
QISO	Compression	–	Compression	–	Compression	–	Compression
OCT	Compression	–	Compression	–	Compression Tensile	–	Compression Tensile Delamination

Table 3: Initial fracture at each strain rate.

Figure 10: Fracture image of UD.
(a) Strain rate 1 /s and -8.2°C (b) Strain rate 0.01 /s and 75 °C

3.3 Fractography and consideration of initial fracture

In addition to fracture observation, fractography of the specimen after the test was performed. Figure 11 shows photographs of a typical UD specimen after testing. From Figure 11 (a), under the conditions of strain rate 1 /s and -8.2 ° C, the specimen was completely separated. And, it is confirmed that it slightly bends to the compression side. From Figure 4 (a), it is estimated that UD breaks beginning at the compression side at low temperature and high strain rate from aspects that the tendencies of the curve shapes at -30 °C and 0 °C are almost similar and that the UD breaks from the compression side at less than 0°C as shown in Figure 10 (a). On the other hand, from Figure 11 (b), it was observed that the specimen did not break but bent under the condition of strain rate 0.01 /s and 75 °C. Similarly, since the tendencies of the curve shapes of 75 °C and 100 °C in Figure 4 (a) are almost similar and wrinkles are generated at the compression side as shown in Figure 10 (b), it is estimated that UD is broken from the onset at the compression side regardless of high or low temperatures.

Figure 12 shows typical photographs of QISO specimen after testing. In the high temperature of 50 ~ 100 °C, flexural deformation was observed, and in 0 ~ 25 °C, it was perfectly broken. At 50 ~ 100 °C, the compression side is somewhat raised, and at 0 ~ 25 °C, the fracture surface slightly warps to the compression side. Comparing the stress-strain curves, it is estimated that the tendencies at 0 ~ 100 °C indicated in Figure 4 (b) are almost similar. From this aspect, it is estimated that the origin of fracture is on the compression side in this temperature range. On the other hand, Figure 12 (a) shows that the

delamination occurred in a wide range in the temperature condition of $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The curve shape in Figure 4 (b) is also different from other temperature conditions. Therefore, it is considered that the delamination is the origin of the fracture at $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 13 shows typical photographs of OCT specimen after testing. It was observed that all specimens broke completely at all temperature conditions. However, the states of the fracture surface are different between the temperature conditions, and the specimens are broken without warping at the lower temperature as shown in Figure 13 (a) and (b), while the fracture surface warps to the compression side on the higher temperature side as shown in Figure 13 (c). Here, from Table 3, it is considered that OCT is broken not only at the compression side but also at the tensile side and the delamination as an origin at a strain rate 1 /s or more. So, it is considered that at the low temperature, the delamination was developed together with the tensile side fracture. On the other hand, the curve shapes at the higher temperature indicated in Figure 4 (c) are almost similar to the curve shapes at the lower strain rate in Figure 5 (c), and the origin of the fracture at the lower strain rate is on the compression side as shown in Table 3, so that the fracture at the higher temperature is also considered to be initiated by the fracture on the compression side.

Figure 11: UD specimen after testing.
 (a) Strain rate 1 /s and $-8.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (b) Strain rate 0.01 /s and $75\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 12: QISO specimen after testing.
 (a) Strain rate 1 /s and $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (b) Strain rate 1 /s and $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (c) Strain rate 1 /s and RT
 (d) Strain rate 1 /s and $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (e) Strain rate 1 /s and $75\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (f) Strain rate 1 /s and $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure 13: OCT specimen after testing.
 (a) Strain rate 1 /s and $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (b) Strain rate 1 /s and RT (c) Strain rate 1 /s and $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

3.4 Strain-rate and temperature dependence of flexural strength

In order to compare the strain rate dependence of each material, the relationship between the flexural strength and the strain rate at room temperature was examined in relation to each material as shown in Figure 14 (a). Normalizing the flexural strengths using the strain rate 1 /s as a reference, the relationship is converted as shown in Figure 14 (b). Figure 14 (b) shows that the tendencies of the strain rate dependence in this strain rate range are almost the same regardless of reinforcement configuration. Figure 15 (a) shows the relationships between flexural strength and temperature at a strain rate of 1 /s. Normalizing the flexural strengths using the room temperature as a reference, the relationship is converted as shown in Figure 15 (b). From Figure 15 (b), a similar temperature dependence was confirmed for all specimens from room temperature to 100 °C. However, OCT showed lower values than UD and QISO at 0 °C. QISO and OCT were lower than UD at 30 °C. These are consistent with the temperature at which the fracture origin of QISO and OCT changed from the compressive side to the tensile side or the delamination. UD has high tensile strength regardless of temperature, while its compressive strength is always lower than the tensile. Therefore, it is inferred that it is always broken at the compression side. On the other hand, in the case of in-plane isotropic OCT and QISO, the difference between tensile strength and compression strength was not as large as UD, and it is inferred that the strength on the compression side exceeded tensile strength and delamination strength by the viscoelasticity of the resin at low temperature. As a result, it was considered that the temperature dependence of flexural strength was smaller than that of UD because it broke before reaching the compression strength in the low temperature side.

Figure 14: Strain rate dependence of each specimen at RT.
 (a) Flexural strength (b) Normalized flexural strength (Reference: Strain rate 1 /s)

Figure 15: Temperature dependence of each specimen at strain rate 1 /s.
 (a) Flexural strength (b) Normalized flexural strength (Reference: RT)

3.5 Strain-rate and temperature dependence of flexural modulus

The strain rate and the temperature dependences on the flexural modulus of each material are compared. Figure 16 (a) shows the relationships between the flexural modulus and the strain rate at room temperature. In addition, normalizing the flexural moduli using the strain rate 1 /s as a reference, the relationship is converted as shown in Figure 16 (b). From Figure 16 (b), it was clarified that the flexural modulus tends to decrease slightly only in OCT at a lower strain rate, but the strain rate dependence in all materials show similar tendency. Figure 17 (a) shows the relationships between the flexural modulus and temperature at strain rate of 1 /s. Normalizing the flexural moduli using the room temperature as a reference, the relationship is converted as shown in Figure 17 (b). It is assumed from Figure 17 (b) that the temperature dependence of QISO is smaller than those of UD and OCT. Here, in the previous research [6], it is reported that flexural modulus is expressed by longitudinal modulus and out-of-plane shear modulus, and especially, the out-of-plane shear modulus contributes to strain rate and temperature dependence. In other words, the lower out-of-plane shear modulus at higher temperature or lower strain-rate affects directly the estimation of the apparatus flexural modulus when the ratio of specimen's thickness to supports distance is high. Conversely, QISO has the smallest thickness among the specimens used in this study, and the effect of out-of-plane shear modulus depending on temperature and strain-rate seems to be small.

Figure 16: Strain rate dependence of each specimen at RT.
 (a) Flexural modulus (b) Normalized flexural modulus (Reference: Strain rate 1 /s)

Figure 17: Temperature dependence of each specimen at strain rate 1 /s.
 (a) Flexural modulus (b) Normalized flexural modulus (Reference: RT)

4 CONCLUSIONS

3-point bending impact test was performed using three kinds of CFRTP with the same matrix resin and reinforced fiber but different reinforced forms. And the strain rate and temperature dependence of flexural strength and flexural modulus were analysed focusing on their difference of reinforcement configuration. Fracture observation by a high speed video camera and fractography of specimen after the test were performed, and fracture behaviors were investigated. Strain rate and temperature dependence was confirmed in flexural strength of all materials, and it was clarified that the tendency changed whether the origin of fracture is on the compressive side or the tensile side. Strain rate dependence of the flexural modulus was small, but strain rate dependence of the flexural modulus was slightly appeared in case of only OCT. Temperature dependence of the flexural modulus was confirmed in UD and OCT. This is because the change of the out-of-plane shear modulus as functions of strain rate and temperature is so large that the flexural deformation is estimated larger at higher temperature and lower strain-rate.

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